

Bodies moving with sound: Effects of pitch and musical sounds on body-representations

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Table S1. Median (range) for questionnaire items (7-point Likert-type items) for the three sound conditions in Experiment 1. * marks significant median differences between conditions.

Variables		Tone		
		Up	Down	Constant
Confidence*	Position 1	6 (4-7)	5 (3-7)	6 (3-7)
	Position 2	6 (3-7)	6 (3-7)	6 (3-7)
Body weight*		3 (1-7)	4 (1-4)	3 (1-5)
Control*		6 (2-7)	5 (3-7)	6 (3-7)
Speed*		5 (2-7)	3 (3-6)	5 (2-7)
Tiredness		3 (1-6)	3 (1-6)	3 (1-5)
Difficulty*		2 (1-6)	3 (1-6)	2 (1-6)
Capability*		6 (2-7)	5 (3-7)	6 (3-7)
Agency		5 (1-7)	5 (2-7)	5 (2-7)
Motivation*		5 (1-7)	4 (2-7)	5 (2-7)
Comfort*		6 (1-7)	4 (2-7)	5 (2-7)

Table S2. Median (range) for questionnaire items (7-point Likert-type items) for all sound conditions in Experiment 2. *D, *T, *P and D*T mark significant median differences due to, respectively, Sound Direction, Timbre, Position and interaction between Sound Direction and Timbre. ^ marks trends towards significance.

Variables		Tone		Musical	
		Up	Down	Up	Down
Confidence *D, *P, *T	Position 1	6 (4-7)	5 (4-7)	6 (4-7)	6 (3-7)
	Position 2	6 (4-7)	6 (4-7)	6 (3-7)	6 (3-7)
Body weight *D D^T		3 (2-6)	4 (2-6)	2 (1-5)	4 (1-7)
Control		6 (3-7)	6 (2-7)	6 (2-7)	6 (1-7)
Speed *D		5 (3-6)	5 (2-7)	5 (2-7)	4 (3-7)
Tiredness D*T		3 (1-5)	3 (1-5)	2 (1-6)	4 (1-6)
Difficulty *D D^T		3 (1-5)	3 (1-5)	2 (1-6)	3 (1-5)
Capability D*T		6 (3-7)	6 (4-7)	6 (3-7)	5 (3-7)
Agency		5 (1-7)	5 (1-7)	6 (1-7)	5 (1-7)
Motivation *D D*T		5 (1-7)	5 (1-7)	5 (4-7)	4 (1-7)
Comfort *D *T D*T		5 (2-7)	4 (2-7)	6 (3-7)	4 (2-7)

Table S3. Median and range questionnaire items (7-point Likert-type items, except for valence and arousal which were 9-point Likert-type) for all sound conditions in Experiment 3. *D, *F and D*F mark significant median differences due to, respectively, Sound Direction, Frequency range and interaction between Sound Direction and Frequency Range. ^ marks trends towards significance.

Variables		Musical Up		Musical Down	
		High	Low	High	Low
7-point Likert	Body Weight *D *F	3 (1-6)	4 (1-6)	3 (1-6)	5 (1-7)
	Control	6 (2-7)	6 (2-7)	6 (2-7)	5 (1-7)
	Speed ^D	5 (2-7)	4 (2-6)	4.5 (3-7)	3 (1-6)
	Tiredness *F D*F	3 (1-5)	3.5 (1-6)	3 (1-5)	4.5 (1-6)
	Difficulty *F	2 (1-4)	3 (1-6)	2.5 (1-5)	3.5 (1-6)
	Capability	6 (2-7)	6 (2-7)	5 (1-7)	5 (2-7)
	Agency	2.5 (1-6)	3 (1-7)	3 (1-6)	2.5 (1-5)
	Motivation *D *F	5 (2-7)	4 (1-7)	5 (2-7)	3 (1-6)
	Comfort *D	5.5 (2-7)	5.5 (2-7)	5 (1-7)	5 (2-7)
	Strength	5 (2-7)	5 (2-7)	4.5 (1-7)	4 (2-7)
	Coordination D* D^F	5.5 (3-7)	6 (2-7)	6 (3-7)	5 (2-7)
9-point Likert	Valence *D *F	6 (3-9)	5 (2-9)	5 (2-8)	5 (2-7)
	Arousal ^D *F	6 (1-9)	5 (2-9)	5 (3-8)	5 (2-8)

Table S4. Detailed summary of results on the effects across all the experiments.

Dimension		Predicted effects	Pitch change	Added Timbre (vs Tone)	Absolute frequency range
Bodily movement		Amplitude	Not affected	Not affected	Increase in movement amplitude (i.e. a higher peak angle) for the “High Pitch” vs “Low Pitch” sounds
		Acceleration/ velocity	Higher maximum upwards acceleration for ascending vs descending pitch	Higher velocity on the upwards movement for the “tone” vs “musical” sounds	Not affected
Proprioceptive awareness		Accuracy of final position	Not affected	Not affected	More accurate for the “Low Pitch” sounds
		Confidence on perceived final position	Feeling more uncertain about their hand position with the descending pitch vs the constant sound (Exp. 1) and vs the ascending pitch sound (Exp. 2)	“Musical” sounds made participants feel more confident about the reached position than “Tone” sounds	Not assessed
		Sense of control	Larger sense of control over the movement with constant vs descending sound	Not affected	Not affected
Bodily feelings and emotional state	Feelings about the body	Weight	Feeling heavier with the descending vs. the ascending or constant sound	The “Musical” sounds maximize the differences between ascending and descending sounds	Feeling lighter with the “High” vs “Low” pitch
		Speed	Feeling slower with the descending vs. the ascending or constant sound	Not affected	Feeling faster with the “High” vs “Low” pitch
		Tiredness	Feeling more tired with the descending vs. the ascending sound	The “Musical” sounds maximize the differences between ascending and descending sounds	Feeling less tired with the “High” vs “Low” pitch Interaction between Sound Direction and Frequency Range: The “Musical_down_Low_pitch” sound made participants feel more tired

		Strength	Not affected	Not assessed	Not affected
Feelings about the movement		Sense of control	Larger sense of control over the movement with constant vs descending sound	Not affected	Not affected
		Ease	Exercise felt easier with the ascending vs descending sound	The “Musical” sounds maximize the differences between ascending and descending sounds	Exercise felt easier with the “High” vs “Low” pitch
		Comfort	Exercise felt more comfortable with ascending vs descending sound	- The “Musical” sounds maximize the differences between ascending and descending sounds - Higher feeling of comfort with the “musical” than with the “tone” sounds	Not affected
		Capability	More capable with ascending vs descending sound	The “Musical” sounds maximize the differences between ascending and descending sounds	Not affected
		Coordination	Movement felt more coordinated with the ascending vs descending sound	Not assessed	Sound Direction and Pitch interaction (not significant): The “Musical_down_Low_pitch” led to feelings of less coordinated movement
Emotional feelings		Motivation	Feeling more motivated with ascending vs descending sound	The “Musical” sounds maximize the differences between ascending and descending sounds	Feeling more motivated with the “High” vs “Low” pitch
		Happiness	Feeling happier with the ascending vs descending sound	Not assessed	Feeling happier with the “High” vs “Low” pitch
		Arousal	Feeling considerably happier with the ascending vs descending sound (not significant)	Not assessed	Feeling considerably more excited with the “High” vs “Low” pitch (not significant)

Figure S1. Barplot with mean and SD for the parameter “Time down” (seconds), for all sound conditions in Experiment 1.

Figure S2. Correlations between self-reported confidence in having reached the requested position and actual task performance (angle deviations from the requested positions) for (A) “Tone_down” and Position 1 in Experiment 1, and (B) “Tone-up”, (C) “Musical_down” and (D) “Musical_up” (both Positions) in Experiment 2.

Figure S3. Bar plot with mean and SD for acceleration and velocity of the upwards movement in Experiment 2. (a) Acceleration in upwards movement for all Sound Conditions in Position 1, and (b) velocity in upwards movement for all Sound Conditions in Position 1.

Figure S4. Bar chart showing the significant effect of the factor Sound Frequency Range on the maximum reached angle (Peak Angle) in Experiment 3.

Figure S5. Boxplots with median(range) score for questionnaire items showing interaction effects between Sound Direction and Sound Frequency Range in Experiment 3. (A) Feelings of tiredness and (B) movement coordination. Down_High_P = Musical_down_High_pitch, Down_Low_P = Musical_down_Low_pitch, Up_High_P = Musical_up_High_pitch, Up_Low_P = Musical_up_Low_pitch.